

Not in My Backyard: Topics of Objection in Housing Development

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GISRUK 2026

Summary

Public objections to building developments can result from multiple causes, including preservationist attitudes of ‘not in my backyard’ (NIMBY). Using natural language processing (NLP) on a unique dataset of over 30,000 free-text responses to proposed residential planning applications in London, we analysed the key themes, sentiment patterns, and differences in public opinion. Whilst we found stereotypically ‘NIMBY’ attitudes, we also found more constructive objections looking to shape the community. In quantitatively describing how and why people object to new developments, we provide policy insights regarding London’s housing crisis.

KEYWORDS: NIMBY, machine learning, natural language processing, smart cities, urban planning.

1 Introduction

In England and Wales following the initial submission of building applications the local planning authority (LPA) must make the application available for community feedback, prior to deciding whether they approve construction. The number of comments received on applications vary greatly, with multiple material comments typically sufficient for the application to be reviewed by the planning board. Commenting on planning applications is one of the few vectors for residents to uninhibitedly voice their opinions about changes to the built environment - representing a key point of interaction between the state, private developer, and community (Ferm et al. (2020)).

Objecting comments often stem from ‘not in my backyard’ (NIMBY) opposition. As outlined by Freudenburg and Pastor (1992) and Lake (1993), NIMBY typically refers to conservative, parochial, and preservationist attitudes. For clarity we refer to this as ‘destructive NIMBYism’. Robinson and Attuyer (2020) and Chatterton (2010) describe a contrasting angle of ‘constructive NIMBYism’, whereby the objections represent more justice seeking community opposition to unsuitable developments, such as unfit proposals by the state, or developers .

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Regardless of whether they are ‘destructive’ or ‘constructive’, opposition to proposed developments can result in projects being delayed, modified, or abandoned altogether. This is particularly pertinent given the housing crisis in the UK. The UK government aims to construct 1.5 million homes before the next general election in 2029, equating to 81,000 residential units per year in London. Given London has rarely exceeded 45,000 completed units in recent years (according to energy performance certificates), Breach (2024) has warned the government targets are unlikely to be met. To this end recent planning reform has sought to minimise objection and maximise build out by simplifying planning processes.

Here we analyse a dataset of community comments received on residential planning applications in eight local authority districts (LADs) in London, alongside information sourced from the Greater London Authority’s Planning London Datahub. This dataset represents a unique source of rich free-text data, reflecting the emergence of new big textual data sources for the analysis of cities as outlined by Reades et al. (2025) and Kitchin (2014). We used methods from natural language processing (NLP) to clean the data and extract metrics and insights. Through the analysis we develop a quantitative characterisation of residents objections to new housing plans, and offer suggestions for how this might inform planning policy in the city.

2 Method

Figure 1: The method used to extract key variables from the data.

2.1 Data

Multiple public datasets were integrated to construct a rich, micro-level description of proposed residential planning applications in London. These included: (i) the Planning London Datahub (PLD), an open database maintained by the Greater London Authority (GLA) that provides detailed

records of planning applications across London; and (ii) a bespoke dataset of community comments collected through web scraping.

Figure 2: A map of greater London with the local authority districts included in the dataset of web-scraped comments highlighted in purple. Local planning authorities which are independent of local authority districts are shown in blue (in the East the London Legacy Development Corporation (LLDC), and the Old Oak and Park Royal Development Corporation (OPDC) in the West).

Community comments were harvested using a custom Python-based web-scraping pipeline. Although these comments are in the public domain, they are not structured for large-scale analysis, and no application programming interfaces (APIs) or standardised data sources exist. We were able to scrape comments relating to 5,071 planning applications filed between 1/1/2021 and 1/1/2025 across eight of the London boroughs: Newham, Southwark, Lambeth, Ealing, the City of London, Brent, Barnet, and Westminster. The applications were included regardless of the local planning authority's decision outcome. Alongside the free-text comments we extracted associated metadata, including application addresses and the comment stance (objecting, supporting, neutral). In total we collated 30,397 comments, of which 27,413 (90.2%) were objections.

	Residential Planning Applications	Residential Units	Total com- ments		Comments per applica- tion	Objections
	n	n	n		mean	mean
Total	5,071	66,476	30,397		5.8	90.2%
Barnet	1,308	10,128	9,262		7.1	89.0%
Brent	935	12,509	2,291		2.5	91.9%
City of London	21	3,899	38		1.8	23.7%
Ealing	1,123	12,182	11,314		10.1	94.6%
Lambeth	545	3,344	2,833		5.2	90.8%
Newham	494	11,258	921		1.9	85.7%
Southwark	308	7,054	2,296		7.8	81.5%
Westminster	497	6,102	1,342		2.7	76.8%

Table 1: Summary statistics of the dataset. Including all comments, and those relating to objections. A map of the regions included is shown in Fig 1.

2.2 Natural Language Processing

In order to extract meaningful insights from the free-text data we applied NLP. Following the methodology of Berragan et al. (2023) first, named entity recognition was used to remove place names and self-identifying proper nouns from the comments in order to reduce location-specific bias and provide anonymity.

Latent topics were identified using BERTopic (Grootendorst (2022)), a popular open-source topic modelling framework that clusters text embeddings based on cosine similarity. The text embeddings were generated using a fine-tuned sentence transformer model to enhance domain-specific semantic representation. Resulting topics were manually reviewed and post-processed to ensure interpretability and thematic coherence.

We also applied sentiment analysis to assign each comment a continuous sentiment score ranging from -1 (highly negative) to $+1$ (highly positive), with 0 indicating neutral sentiment.

2.3 Analysis

The extracted variables were used for downstream analysis. All the code to recreate the analysis can be found here: https://github.com/Bea-Taylor/neighbour_nlp.

3 Results

Table 1 records the key characteristics of the dataset. The number of residential units per planning application ranged from 1 to 1,610 and included a variety of residential build types ranging from fully private developments (4,361 applications with 27,240 units) to social developments (90 applications with 777 units).

Our modelling framework identified 51 objection topics; the most common object was regarding

(a)

(b)

Figure 3: (a) A stacked bar chart showing the 20 most common topics across the objections and their frequency in the dataset across the inner and outer London boroughs. (b) Percentage bar charts showing the frequency of topics across housing types (left) and development sizes (right).

‘construction access’ which was assigned to 18.5% of comments. This was followed by objections on the grounds of the ‘impact on parking’ (13.5%), and the proposal being ‘out of character’ with the local area (7.8%). Grouping them into broader categories, four of the 51 topics referred to short term implications resulting from construction, 30 referred to long term implications of the development, nine referred to impacts to the community, five referred to environmental problems, three referred to problems with the planning process itself.

Figure 3a shows the pattern of topics across inner and outer London. As expected, given the greater number of planning applications filed there, the raw frequency of objections was higher in outer London. The prevalence of topics varied across LADs; whilst parking issues were a point of objection everywhere, in inner London impact on heritage and conservation was almost as important - reflecting both the architectural legacy of the city, as well as variations in the feasibility of public transport and active travel. Figure 3b shows the pattern of topics across developments. Topics of objection was consistent by housing type but varied by development size. Larger developments had more objections relating to the buildings height and density (over-development).

Figure 4: A boxplot of the sentiment score for topics of objection. Of the 51 topics, the plot includes the 10 least angry topics, followed by the 10 most angry topics.

Figure4 presents the mean sentiment score across objection topics. Topics concerning the proposal being perceived as an eyesore exhibit the most negative sentiment, consistent with the emotive

and preservation-oriented nature of such objections. In contrast, comments addressing procedural or technical aspects of the planning process are characterised by comparatively neutral language, indicating lower levels of affective intensity.

4 Discussion and Conclusion

This study demonstrates the novel application of NLP techniques to quantitatively analyse large-scale public participation data within the planning system, reflecting emerging research trends (Reades et al. (2025); Daniel et al. (2024)). By systematically examining free-text objections, we identify recurring thematic patterns that distinguish between what might be characterised as ‘destructive’ and ‘constructive’ forms of NIMBYism. These findings highlight the nuanced motivations underlying public engagement with planning processes, moving beyond qualitative accounts of objection.

The analysis reveals that comments associated with ‘destructive’ NIMBY objections exhibit higher levels of semantically expressed negative sentiment, particularly anger, than other forms of engagement. However, the presence of constructive objections underscores that resistance is not inherently parochial, but can also reflect community resistance and refusal to neoliberal developments as outlined by Fillion et al. (2023) and Tronti (1980). Patterns of objection highlight how communities negotiate the development of their localities, and how refusal (whether symbolic or procedural) functions as an expression of resistance to perceived unwanted change. Such dynamics underscore the importance of treating public commentary not merely as administrative input, but as a substantive component of democratic engagement with the evolving city.

This study has several limitations that point towards directions for future work. First, the dataset is incomplete, covering only eight of London’s 33 local authority districts. Second, participation in planning consultations is subject to self-selection bias, as those who choose to submit comments are more likely to feel empowered and to possess a strong sense of geographic or community identity. In addition, council planning portals capture only formalised modes of engagement, potentially overlooking wider public opinion that is expressed through informal or alternative channels.

There are also important theoretical limitations in distinguishing between ‘constructive’ and ‘destructive’ forms of NIMBYism. The categorisation of objection topics is inherently subjective; for example, concerns framed as ‘over-development’ may be interpreted either as efforts to protect place-based community values or as attempts to preserve existing demographic compositions through the exclusion of perceived outsiders. Such interpretations depend on both social determinants and neighbourhood-specific characteristics, consistent with Soja’s socio-spatial dialectic (Soja (1980)). This highlights the limits of a purely quantitative approach when engaging with the normative dimensions of public objection.

Future work will extend this analysis by integrating richer social demographic data and finer-grained neighbourhood characteristics as per Law et al. (2018). Methodologically, the application of more advanced machine learning approaches, such as random forest models or deep learning architectures, would allow the analysis to move beyond pattern identification toward the prediction of likely public responses. This would enable the estimation of a predictive ‘NIMBY quotient’, capturing expected

levels of objection conditional on development and neighbourhood context.

By aggregating and analysing community perspectives at scale, this approach leverages the collective intelligence embedded in public participation processes. For policymakers (from the MHCLG, the GLA, and the London LADs) such insights offer the potential to better anticipate and respond to community concerns, supporting more context-sensitive, bottom-up approaches to residential development. For example, the quantification of higher public support for council housing initiative could support greater roll-out. Rather than relying solely on centrally imposed numerical housing targets, planning decisions could be informed by a more nuanced understanding of local needs, preferences, and capacities for change (Ferm et al. (2020)).

5 Acknowledgements

We would like to acknowledge the support of the AI for Collective Intelligence (AI4CI) hub.

6 Biography

Beatrice Taylor is a postdoctoral research fellow in the Bartlett Centre for Advanced Spatial Analysis, working on the Smart Cities theme as part of the AI for Collective Intelligence (AI4CI) hub. Her current research focuses on using machine learning methods to analyse how London's built environment is changing.

Adham Enaya is a research fellow, and PhD student, in the Bartlett Centre for Advanced Spatial Analysis. With a background in software engineering, he specialises in developing tools and methods that make urban modelling more accessible.

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